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CURRENT TRENDS IN THE WORLD BEER MARKET AND WAYS TO DEVELOP THE BEER MARKET IN UKRAINE

СУЧАСНІ ТРЕНДИ СВІТОВОГО РИНКУ ПИВА ТА ШЛЯХИ РОЗБУДОВИ РИНКУ ПИВА В УКРАЇНІ

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The Ukrainian beer market is one of the developed markets with high export potential. At the same time, beer production has been declining in recent years. This is explained by Russia's aggression, which led to the destruction and seizure of part of the capacities, a decrease in the standard of living of the population. The beer market is also negatively affected by imperfect state regulation and a significant tax burden. To prepare substantiated proposals to correct the situation, it is advisable to study current trends in the world beer market, the impact of the beer market on economic development, and the EU's experience in regulating this market.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The main trends and problems of alcoholic beverage markets, including beer, ways to solve them are explored in the Green Paper "Analysis of the Fermented Alcoholic Beverages Market" [1], prepared by the Better Regulation Delivery Office. The current state and prospects for the development of the beer market in Ukraine, its structure, and competition strategies in this market are considered in works of V. Bilinchuk, O. Kobylyukh, O. Hirna, S. Rozumey, K. Stupka, etc.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

These works did not sufficiently analyze the trends of the global beer market, there are no effective recommendations for the development of the domestic beer market, and much of the data is outdated.

The aim of the article is to determine, based on a study of world experience, the measures that need to be taken to develop the domestic beer market.

The main part

World beer production in 2023 amounted to 1884 million hectoliters (1 hectoliter - 100 liters). Over the past 10 years, it has decreased by 4.5% (Figure 1). The decrease in beer consumption is associated with a greater commitment of the population of developed countries to a healthy lifestyle, increased competition from other beverages, both alcoholic and non-alcoholic. The global beer market was negatively

Щербак А.В. Сучасні тренди світового ринку пива та шляхи розбудови ринку пива в Україні. Оглядова стаття.

Досліджені тенденції світового ринку пива, причини зростання рівня концентрації на цьому ринку. Обґрунтовано, що завдяки значному мультиплікативному ефекту виробництво пива суттєво впливає на економічний розвиток. Показано, що причинами швидкого зростання кількості крафтових броварень стали підвищення доходів населення та зміна уподобань споживачів, які бажають більшої різноманітності та унікальності смаків. Розглянутий стан крафтового пивоваріння у США та ЄС, заходи його державної підтримки. Проаналізовані ринкові стратегії виробників крафтового пива. Досліджено тенденції ринку пива в Україні, вплив на цей ринок державної політики та агресії Росії. Визначені заходи, які необхідно зробити для розбудови вітчизняного ринку пива у воєнний та повоєнний період.

Ключові слова: пиво, ринок пива, крафтове пиво, розбудова ринку пива, кластер

Shcherbak A.V. Current Trends in the World Beer Market and Ways to Develop the Beer Market in Ukraine. Review article.

The trends of the world beer market and the reasons for the increase in the level of concentration in this market are studied. It is substantiated that, due to the significant multiplier effect, beer production significantly affects economic development. It is shown that the reasons for the rapid growth in the number of craft breweries were the increase in incomes of the population and the change in preferences of consumers who want more variety and uniqueness of tastes. The state of craft brewing in the USA and the EU, its state support measures are considered. The market strategies of craft beer producers are analyzed. The trends of the beer market in Ukraine, the impact of state policy and Russian aggression on this market are studied. The measures that need to be taken to develop the domestic beer market in the war and post-war period are determined.

Keywords: beer, beer market, craft beer, beer market development, cluster

affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, as well as the war in Ukraine, which caused an increase in energy prices and disruptions in global supply chains. The cost of

beer in the leading EU countries in 2023 was 20-25% higher than in 2019.

Figure 1. World beer production in 2014-2023 (million hectoliters)

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2]

Data on beer production in the leading countries are presented in Table. 62.1% of beer production in the world is accounted for by 10 countries. The largest production volumes of this drink are in China and the USA, but production in them is gradually decreasing. At the same time, production is increasing in Brazil and Mexico, which occupy third and fourth place, respectively.

The beer market is undergoing structural changes. According to Eurostat, in 2023, a total of 32.5 billion liters of beer containing alcohol and 1.8 billion liters of

beer without alcohol were produced by EU Member States. At the same time, while the production of beer with alcohol decreased by 5% compared to the previous year, beer without alcohol increased by 13.5% [3]. Beer consumption varies significantly between countries depending on traditions. In Europe, the highest consumption in 2022 was in the Czech Republic: an average of 136 liters per person and Austria – 102 liters. The least consumed in France – 33 liters [4].

Table 1. Beer production in leading producing countries in 2023

Countries	Production volume (million hectoliters)	Share in world production (in %)
1. China	359,1	19,1
2. USA	193,0	10,2
3. Brazil	148,9	7,9
4. Mexico	142,4	7,6
5. Germany	84,9	4,5
6. Russia	83,4	4,4
7. Japan	45,3	2,4
8. Spain	41,3	2,2
9. Poland	35,8	1,9
10. South Africa	35,1	1,9
Total 10 countries	1169,2	62,1
World	1884	100

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2]

The research company John Dunham & Associates conducted a study of the impact of brewing on the US economy in 2022. 92 thousand workers were directly involved in the production and import of beer. At the same time, 137 thousand were employed in the wholesale trade of beer, and 980 thousand in retail sales, including restaurants, bars, shops, etc. 522 thousand are employed in supplier companies, 641 thousand – in other enterprises indirectly related to the production and sale of beer. Taking this into account, brewing creates and supports 2,372 thousand jobs. Each job in the brewing industry contributes to the creation of 30 jobs in other sectors [5].

The brewing sector makes a significant contribution to the productivity, employment and competitiveness of the European economy. 118 thousand people are employed in beer-producing companies in the EU. At the same time, 217 thousand workers are employed by their suppliers, including 68 thousand – by agricultural producers. 1.5 million workers are engaged in the sale of beer in the hospitality sector – bars, pubs, restaurants, etc., 220 thousand – in retail trade. Total employment related to the production and sale of beer is 2 million. This is about 1% of all employment in the European Union [6]. Thus, each job in the EU brewing industry contributes to the creation of 17 jobs in other sectors. The

difference with the US data is explained by differences in methodology: in Europe, employment in enterprises indirectly related to the production and sale of beer is not taken into account.

The total contribution to the value added of EU countries is 52 billion euros, which is comparable to the GDP of some of them. Taxes received in the beer supply chain exceeded 40 billion euros in 2022.

Until the second half of the 19th century, beer was produced by small breweries and sold to local consumers. However, the industrial revolution allowed for the mechanization of production, pasteurization made it possible to store beer for longer, and railways reduced transportation costs. As a result, economies of scale of production increased significantly, which led to the closure of many enterprises. If in 1873 there were 4131 breweries in the USA, then in 1900 – 1816, and in 1950 – 350. The process of concentration significantly accelerated in the second half of the 20th century, which was also associated with the development of the media. In 1950, only 9% of US households had a television, and ten years later – almost all. This gave a significant advantage to large manufacturers, who could advertise their products on television. If in 1947 the share of the four largest companies in beer production in the USA was about 20%, then in 2000 the share of the three largest was 81%. Similar processes took place in other countries and in the world market as a whole. The share of the 10 largest companies in world beer production in 2023 was 69.1% [2].

The world market leader is Anheuser Busch InBev, headquartered in Belgium. The number of employees is over 150 thousand. The company has about 630 beer brands in 150 countries. Together with its subsidiaries, it produced 505.9 million hectoliters of beer in 2023, its share in the global market was 26.9%. This company produces twice as much beer as the Dutch company Heineken, which ranks second. A few years ago, the Danish company Carlsberg was in third place, but now it has been replaced by the Chinese company China Resources Snow Breweries, remaining in fourth place.

Large companies chose product characteristics that allowed them to attract as many consumers as possible. As a result, beer became homogeneous, standardized, and lost its unique taste characteristics. However, not everyone likes uniformity. This led to the emergence of craft brewing. It is believed that it began in San Francisco in 1965 as a result of the purchase of Anchor Brewing Company by F. Maytag. However, the mass emergence of craft breweries is associated with the deregulation of the beer market in the United States in the late 1970s, when the ban on home production of this drink was lifted and its production for personal and family consumption was no longer taxed. This led to a colossal increase in the number of craft breweries in the United States: if in 1979 there were only 2, then in 2012 – 2037, and in 2020 – 8764.

The American Brewers Association (ABA) defines craft breweries as "small", "independent" and "traditional". Small refers to size: annual production volume less than 6 million barrels (7 million

hectoliters). Independence refers to ownership (less than 25% of the brewery owned or controlled by alcohol industry member who is not a craft brewer). Craft beer producers use traditional recipes, making beer from malt. At the same time, they introduce many innovations, adding various ingredients, including non-traditional ones (potatoes, aloe, cucumbers, etc.).

The prerequisites for the craft revolution were an increase in incomes and changing preferences of consumers, who want more variety and unique flavors. Craft beer is especially popular among young people. At the same time, in developing countries and countries with economies in transition, it is sold much less, which is associated with its high cost.

According to the American Brewers Association, the share of small and independent breweries in beer production in the United States in 2023 was 13.3%. Given the higher cost of craft beer, its share in retail sales was 24.7%. The craft revolution also affected Europe. The number of breweries in the EU increased by 1.5 times during 6 years (2016-2022) - from 6,225 to 9,684.

According to the EU Council Directive 92/83/EEC of 19 October 1992 on the harmonisation of the structures of excise duties on alcohol and alcoholic beverages", EU Member States are allowed to use a reduced rates of excise duty on beer produced by small breweries (with a volume of up to 200,000 hectoliters). The rates can be reduced to 50%, which allows to increase the competitiveness of such enterprises. These tax incentives have been implemented in 23 countries and apply to 95% of breweries that produce 5% of beer. At the same time, in some EU countries the rate reduction is less than 50% or the incentives are used for enterprises that produce less beer compared to the level established in the Directive 92/83/EEC. In 2018, the excise duty was halved in the USA for breweries that produce less than 60 thousand barrels (70 thousand hectoliters) of beer per year.

The market strategies of large producers and craft breweries are fundamentally different. The former focus on large groups of consumers, selling their products at affordable prices. The cost of craft beer is much higher, so its producers use a niche strategy, relying on product differentiation. This allows them to form groups of loyal consumers who are willing to pay more for beer with unique flavors. Craft breweries produce products in small batches, so they can afford to experiment with recipes and new ingredients.

Craft breweries usually sell their products in a specific area. Unlike large enterprises, they rarely spend money on advertising in print media, on television, radio. Instead, they use the Internet, social networks, sponsor certain events, charities, etc.

The differences between regular and craft breweries are not clear. The American Brewers Association initially considered craft breweries with a beer production volume of less than 2 million barrels per year, but then raised the limit to 6 million barrels.

Craft brewers actively cooperate with each other. The members of the American Brewers Association are 6,500 brewers, as well as representatives of related sectors, wholesalers and retailers of beer. The goal of

the Association is to promote and protect craft beer producers. A number of programs are implemented aimed at training, promoting the export of products, festivals, conferences, etc. are organized. In 2017, the Association introduced the craft brewer's mark, which allows consumers to distinguish craft beer from products of other manufacturers. A subdivision of the Brewers Association is the American Home Brewers Association, which has 30 thousand members.

In the UK, the Society of Independent Brewers and Associates (SIBA) has been operating since 1980, representing the interests of independent brewing companies. SIBA's mission is to provide a fair playing field for its members, to increase their profitability and market share. The organisation has achieved a tax system that allows smaller breweries to pay less tax. In 2002, SIBA launched the Beerflex direct delivery scheme (DDS) to help small brewers promote and sell their beer.

DDS now buys over 4,500 draught and bottled beers from around 450 participating SIBA brewers and sells them on to 12 national pub companies and off-trade retailers – companies with which, until the establishment of Beerflex, brewers of local beers found it extremely difficult to trade [7]. Beerflex DDS receives orders from a company or outlet direct via e-mail, telephone or via SIBA's Online Order Portal and

distribute them on a daily basis to Beerflex brewing members. Brewers who cooperate with Beerflex have the necessary certificates, so customers can be sure that they are receiving quality beer.

Cooperation between craft brewers also takes place at the local level. They exchange resources and information, recommend other breweries to their customers. In a number of regions, network communities are being formed, which are trying to take market share from large producers by joining forces.

A study conducted in the USA showed that most craft breweries are concentrated in several states. New breweries are created primarily in regions with a large number of existing ones. For example, in the state of New Jersey, the number of breweries increased from 22 in 2012 to 130 in 2020. At the same time, the vast majority of them are concentrated in three districts. The emergence of "brewing districts" facilitates connections with suppliers, promotes the expansion of cooperation between brewers, and allows to attract visitors who want to taste different types of beer.

The geographical concentration of breweries contributes to the formation of clusters. One of the most effective is the San Diego craft beer cluster, located in California. San Diego is called the capital of craft beer. The cluster scheme is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. San Diego Craft Beer Cluster
Source: compiled by authors on materials [8]

The core of the cluster is more than 150 craft breweries. They produce a full range of craft beer. But the most popular style is double Indian pale ale, which is characterized by high hop content and a bitter taste. About half of the products are sold locally thanks to a developed network of pubs, bars, and restaurants. Wholesale and retail enterprises also play an important role in the cluster. The formation of the cluster was facilitated by local demand conditions. California is characterized by a high standard of living and there are many people who are inclined to experiment and want variety.

Suppliers of malt, hops, and production equipment are mainly located outside the cluster. However, San Diego is home to White Lab, one of the largest yeast producers. By studying beer samples in the company's laboratory, brewers improve production and introduce new types of products. California State University San Marcos and San Diego State University collaborate

with the cluster. San Marcos University offers the EngiBeer program, which teaches students how to brew craft beer, as well as create and manage a brewery. Many graduates have opened breweries in the region. The San Diego Brewers Guild organizes festivals, conduct market research, and lobby the cluster's interests in government structures [8]. The brewing industry also contributes to the economy of San Diego County through tourism. Brewery tours are organized, and hundreds of thousands of people come to festivals and beer weeks.

The study "The Impact of Craft Breweries on the Economy of San Diego County" states that 3,600 people were employed in the production and sale of craft beer in this county in 2020, including indirect activities – 4,039. The total volume of economic activity associated with the production and sale of craft beer in San Diego County is between \$290 million and \$330 million. It should be noted that this is data for a

year when beer production has significantly decreased due to the pandemic. In 2018, the total volume of economic activity associated with the production and sale of craft beer was between \$480 million and \$590 million dollars, and the number of employees was 24% higher [9].

Brewing has become one of the few sectors of the Ukrainian economy, where for a long time production significantly exceeded the 1990 level and the quality of products has significantly increased. This was primarily due to the arrival of powerful foreign companies: Anheuser Busch InBev, Carlsberg. However, Russia's aggression led to a reduction in beer production and consumption. Beer production in 2024 amounted to 140 million dekaliters, which is 2.2 times less than in 2021 and is 82.4% of the volume of 2021.

Among the factors that negatively affect the beer market are those related to state policy. This market is characterized by a significant tax and regulatory burden. Beer producers pay an excise duty of UAH 2.78 per liter of drink, as well as a number of other taxes. Beer producers must obtain licenses for the production and wholesale of alcoholic beverages, certificates of alcoholic beverage production, etc.

The beer market is important for the economic development of Ukraine. This is primarily due to the significant multiplier effect of this market. In this regard, the reduction in beer production negatively affects a number of markets. On the other hand, the rise in this market leads to a significant increase in employment, primarily in trade and the services sector.

The beer market also affects the health of the population. In Ukraine, more than half of alcohol is consumed in the form of strong drinks, while in Western European countries -15-20% [10]. This is one of the most important reasons why morbidity and mortality due to alcohol consumption in our country significantly exceeds the rates of most EU countries. Therefore, it is important to continue the process of replacing vodka with beer.

On June 18, 2024, the Law of Ukraine "On State Regulation of the Production and Circulation of Ethyl Alcohol, Alcohol Distillates, Bioethanol, Alcoholic Beverages, Tobacco Products, Tobacco Raw Materials, Liquids Used in Electronic Cigarettes, and Fuel" was adopted. It provides for certain measures to simplify economic activity in these markets. In particular, the concept of "small beer production" is introduced. This is a business entity that carries out the production of beer in a volume not exceeding 10 thousand hectoliters (1 million liters) per year using premises that are physically separated from the territory of any other brewery, and which does not produce beer on the basis of an agreement (license) for the right to use the trademark or production process of another manufacturer.

Small beer producers have the right to wholesale beer without obtaining an appropriate license. The relevant business entities don't have to obtain a certificate of alcoholic beverages production. Instead, they submit to the regulatory authorities a declaration of compliance of the material and technical base with the requirements of the legislation.

The Action plan for the implementation of the UA-EU Association Agreement provides for consideration of the feasibility of establishing reduced rates of excise duty for independent small breweries. On May 20, 2021, the draft Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Article 215 of the Tax Code of Ukraine on Establishing Reduced Rates of Excise Duty on Alcoholic Beverages (Beer) for Small Beer Producers" (No. 5118 dated February 19, 2021) was adopted in the first reading. It provides for a halving of the rate of excise duty on beer for small beer producers, setting it at the level of UAH 1.39 per 1 liter. However, this bill has not been considered later, which is most likely due to the impossibility of providing new tax incentives in wartime conditions. It is advisable to adopt it after the end of the war. This will stimulate, first of all, the production of craft beer.

At the same time, it should be borne in mind that in the EU Council Directive 92/83/EEC, small breweries are considered to be business entities that produce less than 200 thousand hectoliters (20 million liters) per year. It is advisable to introduce such a definition to the Ukrainian legislation, simplifying the business conditions for all domestic enterprises that produce less than this volume, and in the future - to provide them with excise duty tax incentives.

To develop the beer market in the post-war period, it is also necessary:

- development of cooperation between craft beer producers, creation a powerful organization that should represent their interests. In Ukraine, there are a number of organizations that unite craft beer producers: the Association of Independent Breweries of Ukraine, the Association of Beer Producers and Fans, the Association of Independent Brewers of Ukraine, etc. At the same time, the experience of developed countries indicates the need to consolidate efforts and create one powerful organization.
- creation of a system of direct beer delivery. The experience of the UK shows that this will help craft brewers to promote and sell their products;
- promotion of the creation of craft beer clusters. This will improve product promotion, increase the competitiveness of market entities;
- promotion of the organization of beer festivals, the development of beer tourism. This will increase beer production and employment in trade and the service sector.

Conclusion

The importance of beer production in the economy is largely due to a significant multiplier effect: it contributes to the creation of a large number of jobs in related markets. The global beer market is characterized by a high level of concentration: the share of the 10 largest companies was 69.1% in 2023. At the same time, the number of craft breweries has been growing rapidly in recent decades. The reasons for this were the increase in incomes and the change in consumer preferences. Craft brewers actively cooperate, and in some regions they form network communities that are trying to take market share from

large producers. In the USA and the EU, small breweries have received significant tax incentives.

The development of brewing based on state support is of great importance for Ukraine. To increase the competitiveness of domestic beer producers, it is necessary to simplify the conditions of economic activity, reduce the rates of excise for small producers,

form a powerful organization of craft beer producers, promote the creation of a system of direct beer supply, promote the development of beer tourism and craft beer clusters.

The prospects for further research are associated with the active study of the best foreign experience with the aim of its implementation in Ukraine.

Abstract

The production and personnel potential available in Ukraine allows us to satisfy domestic demand and establish large-scale beer exports. However, in recent years, production has been decreasing, while beer import has been increasing. In order to prepare reasonable proposals for improving the situation, a thorough study of world experience is necessary.

The purpose of the article is to determine, based on a study of world experience, the measures that need to be taken to develop the domestic beer market.

The trends of the world beer market are analyzed, the largest producers are identified. The reasons for the high level of concentration in this market are clarified. It is substantiated that, due to the significant multiplier effect, beer production significantly affects economic development. The causes and consequences of the development of craft brewing, measures of its state support in the USA and the EU are analyzed. The strategies of craft brewers are studied. Craft brewers are shown to be actively collaborating, and in some regions, forming network communities that are trying to take market share away from large producers. The features of the San Diego craft beer cluster and its contribution to the economy of the district are considered.

The state and trends of the beer market in Ukraine, the impact of state policy and Russian aggression on this market are studied. The measures to simplify the conditions of economic activity, implemented in this market recently, are considered. Proposals are made for the development of the beer market in Ukraine.

The development of brewing based on state support is of great importance for the post-war reconstruction of Ukraine. To increase the competitiveness of domestic beer producers, it is necessary to simplify the conditions of economic activity, reduce the rates of excise duty for small producers, form a powerful organization of craft beer producers, promote the creation of a system of direct beer supply, the development of beer tourism and craft beer clusters.

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